

Enhanced Charge Separation Efficiency in DNA Templated Polymer Solar Cells

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Abstract

The insertion of a DNA nano-layer into polymer based solar cells, between the Electron Transport Layer (ETL) and the active material, is proposed to improve the charge separation efficiency. Complete bulk heterojunction donor-acceptor solar cells of the layered type Glass/Electrode (ITO)/ETL/ P3HT:PC₇₀BM /hole transport layer/Electrode (Ag) are investigated using femtosecond transient absorption spectroscopy both in the NIR and the UV-Vis regions of the spectrum. By varying the composition of the ETL we observe a change in the spectral and temporal response of the transient absorption

of the cells. The spectral changes indicate that when the DNA is deposited on the ZnO nanoparticles (ZnO-NPs) in the ETL it can imprint a different long range order on the P3HT polymer which is subsequently spin coated on top of the ETL with respect to the non-ZnO-NPs/DNA containing cells. This leads to a faster quenching of the excited exciton signal of the polymer which has been attributed to more efficient exciton dissociation. Finally, the temporal response of the NIR absorption shows that the DNA promotes more efficient production of charge transfer states and free polarons in the P3HT cation indicating that the increased exciton dissociation correlates with increased charge separation.

1. Introduction

Bulk Heterojunction (BHJ) solar cells in which an oligothiophene polymer acts as a photoabsorber and electron donor (D) and a fullerene derivative acts as an acceptor (A) have been intensely investigated in recent years.¹ The reason being that high power conversion efficiencies (PCEs) have been achieved for these cells largely thanks to the efficient exciton formation and subsequent dissociation at the D/A interface.^{1,2} Together with solar cell engineering, including efficient electron and hole transport layers, PCEs higher than 11 % have been achieved.³ This type of cell is particularly versatile as the thin film can be deposited on numerous substrates including, for example, flexible transparent plastics making them ideal for certain applications such as building integrated photovoltaics.⁴

A great deal of research has been invested in optimizing the performance of these cells by tailoring the chemical structures of the donors and acceptors (e.g.⁵), optimizing the nanomorphology of the D/A blend,⁶ and the Electron and Hole Transport Layers (ETL and HTL) to improve charge transport and injection to the electrodes (e.g.⁷) as well as tuning the work function of the ETL.⁸

Clearly, in order to optimize the conversion efficiency of a solar cell it is necessary to have a detailed understanding of the dynamics of charge formation from the photoabsorption all

the way through to the charge collection at the electrodes. The generally accepted time line can be summarized as follows⁹ : i) photogeneration of the exciton in the polymer, ii) exciton diffusion to the BHJ interface, iii) charge transfer to the fullerene and formation of a charge transfer state (CTS, also sometimes called a bound polaron pair), iv) complete charge separation, and v) diffusion of the resulting polarons to the ETL/HTL and subsequent injection into the electrodes. The overall efficiency of the solar cells depends on several factors including the quantum efficiency which is affected by the efficiency of the above processes but also by the photon absorption, exciton quenching, charge separation and charge extraction. In spite of a great deal of research on these topics there are still a number of controversies over the details of some of these processes including for example, the details of structure in the visible absorption of the polymers,¹⁰⁻¹³ the extent of delocalization of the initially excited exciton,¹⁴⁻¹⁷ the role of morphology^{18,19} and molecular orientation on the dynamics,²⁰ and the extent of participation of hot and cold excitons in the charge separation process.²¹⁻²⁴

Futhermore, it has been known for some time that different regioregularities²⁵⁻²⁸ and morphologies^{6,27,29} of the P3HT part of the blend can have a strong influence on the optical and electrical properties as well as the charge generation and recombination dynamics of the solar cells in general with a resulting knock-on effect on their efficiency.^{30,31} For example, even small changes in the regioregularity of the P3HT used in the blend (86% to 96%) induce important consequences on the crystallinity of the P3HT in the Polymer Solar Cell (PSC) and subsequently on the efficiency of these cells.³² Other, important factors controlling the morphology/crystallinity of the P3HT in the blend include polymer molecular weight, solvent used in deposition,³³⁻³⁵ deposition method (drop casting, spin coating, etc.), annealing (thermal or solvent vapor)^{36,37} and the substrate.³⁸ In many of these cases either the UV-Vis absorbance or the transient absorption (UV-Vis and NIR) have been used to characterize the final quality of the P3HT.³⁹⁻⁴¹ Therefore, it is quite reasonable that the change in the substrate induced by the layer of DNA prior to spin coating of the P3HT/PCBM blend (see Solar Cell Preparation for details of the device manufacture) can have important consequences on

the long-range order/crystallinity/aggregation of the P3HT in that layer.

Furthermore, a great deal of research has been carried out to demonstrate the relations between polymer morphology and BHJ solar cell performance.^{40,42} With this result in mind we propose a new route to obtain ordered structures of P3HT by the deposition of a DNA nano-layer on the ZnO-NPs ETL which acts as a template for the subsequent P3HT deposition. The presence of DNA does not negatively affect the performance of the cells as demonstrated in a previous paper by some of the authors,⁸ and indeed the DNA nano-layer improves the carrier extraction efficiency of the cells by lowering the work function of the ETL.^{8,43} In the same publication it was shown by AFM and STM on the ITO/ZnO-NPs and ITO/ZnO-NPs/DNA substrates that the latter is smoother and contains elongated regular structure on the surface not visible on the ITO/ZnO-NPs substrate.

In this letter we demonstrate that the addition of DNA to the ETL of an inverted ITO/ZnO-NPs(ETL)/P3HT:PC₇₀BM/MoO₃(HTL)/Ag cell (schematically shown in Figure 1 (a)) has multiple effects on the dynamics of photocharge generation. We aim to show that when the DNA is deposited on the ZnO nanoparticles the subsequent spin coating of the polymer blend allows the DNA to imprint a different long range structure on the polymer with respect to the solar cells not containing ZnO-NPs/DNA. The resulting structure is more efficient at extracting the initially formed excitons into separated polarons. These aspects have been extracted from a detailed analysis of the UV-Vis and NIR Transient Absorption (TA) of complete solar cells following photoexcitation. An important aspect of this work is the use of a comparative technique in which we compare the TA spectra of different solar cells by varying the ETL components. As a result we do not discuss in detail the absolute values of the time decay constants but only the relative values on changing the composition of the ETL. All solar cells were assembled/produced at the same time and investigated spectroscopically within a short period so that cell degradation would not have any effect on the measurements. Furthermore, the PCEs of the cells were measured before and after the ultrafast measurements (see Table 1.)

2. Results and Discussion

The following discussion is divided into two parts: first we present the spectral analysis of the static and transient absorption spectra, where the shifts of the peaks (in wavelength) of the TA spectra are discussed in order to demonstrate the change of the P3HT morphology due to the presence of the DNA layer; we then discuss the temporal analysis, where the behavior of the cells is studied in a delay time range between 50 fs and 500 ps, in order to correlate the morphology of the P3HT induced by DNA with the improved charge separation efficiency.

The absorbances of cells of the type Glass/ITO/ETL/P3HT:PC₇₀BM/MoO₃/Ag with a) ETL = nothing, b) ETL = DNA, c) ETL = ZnO-NPs and d) ETL = ZnO-NPs/DNA are shown in Figure 1 (b). The power conversion efficiencies of these cells are shown to have the following values: a) 1.17%, b) 3.22%, c) 3.43%, d) 4.09% (see Table 1 for details). Furthermore, the photovoltaic parameters of these cells including the short circuit current (J_{sc}), the fill factor (FF) and the open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) are also summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Averages of the PV parameters of P3HT:PC₇₀BM based inverted polymer solar cells made with different ETLs over four different samples: ITO only, ITO/DNA, ITO/ZnO-NPs, and ITO/ZnO-NPs/DNA composite layer.

Device	J_{sc} [mA/cm²]	V_{oc} [V]	FF [%]	PCE [%]
Only ITO	10.54 ± 0.44	0.269 ± 0.004	41.51 ± 0.22	1.17 ± 0.05
ITO/DNA	11.17 ± 0.07	0.543 ± 0.005	50.41 ± 0.74	3.22 ± 0.02
ITO/ZnO-NPs	9.92 ± 0.730	0.572 ± 0.002	60.63 ± 2.21	3.43 ± 0.10
ITO/ZnO-NPs/DNA	11.86 ± 0.72	0.588 ± 0.004	58.71 ± 3.12	4.09 ± 0.01

The absorption in the visible range is dominated mainly by the $\pi - \pi^*$ absorption of the P3HT polymer. In the case of pristine regioregular-P3HT (rr-P3HT) films there are three peaks¹⁰ which are centered at 610 (A₁), 570 (A₂) and 520 nm (A₃) but are strongly overlapped, similar to what is observed here in Figure 1 (b). There are various models present in the literature which are used to describe the absorption peaks.^{10-13,44} The details of these models are fascinating but they are not central to the present work as the most

Figure 1: (a) Schematic diagram of the Glass/ITO/ETL/P3HT:PC₇₀BM/MoO₃/Ag with ETL = nothing, ETL = DNA, ETL = ZnO-NPs and ETL = ZnO-NPs/DNA solar cells. (b) Steady state absorption of the solar cells examined in this work.

important point to be taken from these discussions is that the wavelengths of the A₂ and A₃ peaks are dependent on the degree of long range order and conjugation length of the polymer chains while the position of the A₁ peak is quite insensitive to these parameters. This point is strongly supported by empirical evidence reported in literature.^{10,45}

While there are only small differences in the static UV-Vis spectra (see Figure 1 (b)) between the different solar cells, this is not true in the case of the TA spectra as will be described below.

Ultrafast optical spectroscopy has been used extensively to determine the time scales and efficiencies of the above described processes in BHJ devices.^{7,31,37,45–55} The particular form of ultrafast spectroscopy used in this work is TA spectroscopy in which an optical pump excites the sample and a white light continuum probes the photoinduced effects at a variable delay time.

The optical pump pulse used in this work (405 nm, 3.06 eV) principally excites the P3HT thus generating an exciton which then eventually leads to charge separation and collection at the electrodes following the steps outlined in the introduction. Some excitons will also be formed in PC₇₀BM but for the remainder of this discussion we will concentrate on the fate of the P3HT excitons as these are the species that we follow spectroscopically.

The TA spectra are shown in Figure 2 where the principal features one can observe are

Figure 2: Pseudocolor NIR transient absorption maps for the Glass/ITO/ETL/P3HT:PC₇₀BM/MoO₃/Ag cells with a) ETL = ZnO and b) ETL = ZnO/DNA. Pseudocolor UV-Vis transient absorption maps of c) ETL = ZnO-NPs and d) ETL = ZnO-NPs/DNA, e) ETL = nothing, and f) ETL = DNA solar cells. It should be noted that there is a change from linear to log scale on the temporal axis at 10 ps.

i) photoinduced absorption (positive ΔA) in the region between 620 and 1300 nm which can be further divided into features PIA₁ to PIA₅ (see for example Figure 2 (a) and (c)), and ii) photoinduced bleaching (negative ΔA) in the wavelength region 470 - 620 nm (2.0 - 2.75 eV) which can be further divided into the features labeled PB₁, PB₂ and PB₃ as shown in Figures 2 (c) - (f). These features are common to the TA spectra of all blended P3HT polymers and we rely on the comprehensive literature to make an assignment of each of these features.^{24,31,37,47} If we first consider the photoinduced absorption region it is found that the PIA₁ to PIA₄ features are generally assigned to a number of overlapping features due to

Figure 3: Spectral cuts at probe a delay of 800 fs of the transient absorption following optical pumping of the Glass/ITO/ETL/P3HT:PC₇₀BM/MoO₃/Ag with ETL = nothing, ETL = DNA, ETL = ZnO-NPs and ETL = ZnO-NPs/DNA solar cells.

absorption of the CTS (also called a bound polaron pair), and the delocalized and localized hole polaron in the P3HT^{7,37} while the PIA₅ is commonly associated with absorption of the initially excited singlet exciton. The PIA₂ and PIA₃ are likely to be the same feature just spectrally situated on either side of 800 nm and thus present in both the UV-Vis and NIR spectra. The photoinduced bleaching in the visible region, PB₁, PB₂ and PB₃ which correspond reasonably well with the energies of the A₁, A₂ and A₃ transitions in the static UV-Vis spectra are generally assigned to ground state bleaching.²⁴ However, if this was indeed the case the time dependence of the PB₁, PB₂ and PB₃ signals should reflect the population of the ground state and therefore should all be equal. This is clearly not the case as can be seen from visual inspection of Figures 2 (c) - (f) where it is clear that the PB₂ and PB₃ typically have shorter lifetimes than PB₁. We therefore attribute at least part of these signals to photoinduced emission or transition blocking due to state filling of the excited state. In either case, the intensities of the signals PB₁, PB₂ and PB₃ depend on the

populations of the corresponding excited states which, having different lifetimes, can confer different temporal behaviors on these signals.

We start with the spectral analysis in the visible range by making a spectral cut of the TA spectra shown in Figure 2 at a time delay of 800 fs. These cuts are reported in Figure 3, where the intensity of the signals have been normalized to the minimum of the PB_1 . The first point to note is that the PB_1 signal at 610 nm (2.1 eV) exhibits very little spectral changes on the modification of the ETL. From the above discussion on the steady state absorption of P3HT it was noted that this peak in general is largely insensitive to the degree of order of the P3HT. The region of the TA spectra containing the PB_2 and PB_3 features, on the other hand, exhibits significant variation in the peak wavelength behaviors of the signals with varying composition of the ETL including a strong spectral shift of the PB_2 to the blue which is particularly visible in the cell with the ZnO-NPs/DNA ETL while the other cells show much smaller shifts. This suggests that the ZnO-NPs/DNA has an effect on the regularity of the intrachain order of the P3HT. Furthermore, the conjugation length and long range order play a role in the degree of intrachain coupling. So the suggestion is that the DNA layer imprints a different conjugation length and long range order when the P3HT blend layer is applied on top of the DNA. In the case of PB_3 a new feature at 510 nm appears in the ETL = ZnO-NPs/DNA cell (PB_3^*) in addition to the original PB_3 of the other cells at 470 nm. The overlap of these signals makes it difficult to assess the spectral and temporal behaviors of the individual components therefore we concentrate on PB_1 and PB_2 for the remainder of the text.

It should be noted that the ITO/DNA solar cell shows only small shifts of the signals of the PB_2 and PB_3 features with respect to ITO/ZnO-NPs and only ITO. This may initially seem surprising considering that we assign the morphology change of the P3HT to the presence of the DNA. This lack of change of the morphology of the P3HT in the ITO/DNA containing solar cell is assigned to the fact that the surface area of ITO/DNA is significantly lower than that of ITO/ZnO-NPs/DNA. Indeed, it is the roughness of the ZnO-NPs layer

that increases the surface area of ITO/ZnO-NPs/DNA, which consequently increases the contact area between P3HT and DNA, and therefore the effect of the DNA layer on P3HT is maximized.

Figure 4: Spectral cuts in NIR at delay times of (a) 1 ps and (b) 500 ps for PSC with ETL = ZnO-NPs (blue line) and ETL = ZnO-NPs/DNA (red line).

NIR probing^{31,45,50-55} has been of great use in the investigation of the dynamics of PSCs. In this work, the TA in the NIR has been measured for the PSCs with ETL=ZnO and ETL=ZnO-NPs/DNA and both are dominated by three areas of PIA (See Figure 4). The largest signal at short times is in the range 1200-1250 nm (PIA₅) and has generally been attributed to the excited state absorption of the singlet exciton.^{50,53} An interesting point to note is that while the central wavelength of PIA₅ in the ZnO-NPs cell is at 1214 nm that of

the ZnO-NPs/DNA cell is shifted to longer wavelengths at approx. 1250 nm. This red shift has been associated with a larger delocalization of the exciton,^{53,56} which in turn is related to an increase of the intra-chain order of the P3HT.³¹ In any case the different wavelength of this absorption supports the conclusion that the ZnO-NPs/DNA cell imposes a different long range order on the P3HT and furthermore leads to a larger delocalization of the initially excited exciton. It should be noted that changes in the P3HT/PC₇₀BM interface can have effects of delocalization of the exciton and thus on the charge separation efficiency.^{57,58} The remaining two features (PIA₃ and PIA₄) evident at longer delay times in Figure 4(b), are centered at 840 and 980 nm, respectively. These have been assigned to overlapping features due to the bound polaron pair and the separated polaron in P3HT.³¹ These appear to have the same spectral content in both cells but with a very slightly higher intensity of the polaron signal in the ZnO-NPs/DNA cell at long times (see Figure S1 in the supporting information).

Having discussed the spectral behavior of the photobleaching response we now concentrate on the temporal analysis of the PB₁ and PB₂ features which reflect the population of the corresponding excited states. The temporal response has been extracted from the TA data by fitting the part of the spectrum containing PB₁ and PB₂ by two Gaussian functions and then plotting the amplitude of the fits as a function of time (see Figure 5). The significant difference (and more directly related to the efficiency of the cells) is in the temporal evolution of the PB₂ signal as is clearly seen in Figure 5. The main difference in the PB₂ evolution between ETL=ZnO-NPs and ETL=ZnO-NPs/DNA cells is that there is a smaller contribution of the long-time tail and the appearance of two decay times of 5 and 100 ps (in addition to the 1 ps timescale present in all cells) in the ETL=ZnO-NPs/DNA cells (see Table S2). Furthermore, it can be seen that there is a general trend for a smaller contribution of the long-time tail to the PB₂ signal on going from ETL = nothing to ZnO-NPs/DNA (see Figure S2 and Table S2 in the Supporting Information). The overall effect correlates well with the PCE of cells and therefore we propose that the long time scale is due to trapping of the exciton states into defects in the P3HT crystalline phase. The appearance of two

Figure 5: The intensities of the (a) PB₁ and (b) PB₂ signals as a function of delay time between the 400 nm optical pump and the visible probe for the Glass/ITO/ETL/P3HT:PC₇₀BM/MoO₃/Ag with ETL = ZnO-NPs and ETL = ZnO-NPs/DNA solar cells.

intermediate timescales in the ETL=ZnO-NPs/DNA cells can be interpreted as additional charge separation mechanisms which are possible due to the longer lifetime of the untrapped excitons in these cells. Clearly the smaller the contribution of the signal at long time delays the higher the fraction of excitons extracted from the P3HT phase into CT states at the interface, the higher the amount of separated charges and thus the higher the efficiency of the cell. It should be noted that the short timescale decay of 1 ps which is due to bimolecular recombination as demonstrated by power dependence studies (see Figure S3) is not significantly affected by the ETL (see values for τ_1 in Table S2 in the supporting information).

The temporal evolution of the PIA₃, PIA₄ and PIA₅ signals are shown in Figure S2. The PIA₃, PIA₄ bands have been assigned to overlapping features due to the bound and free polarons in P3HT while the PIA₅ band is due to the singlet exciton. The lack of a significant difference in the temporal behavior of the singlet exciton (PIA₅), is somewhat surprising considering the above discussions where it was shown that the dissociation of excited/hot excitons is more efficient in the ZnO-NPs/DNA containing cells. A possible explanation is that the PIA in the NIR is more sensitive to the ground state excitons than the excited states. Another point to note is that all signals exhibit a sub 100 fs rise time, followed by two exponential decays with times constants on the order of 1 ps and hundreds of ps, respectively. The ultrafast risetime of the polaron signals (PIA₃ and PIA₄) has been observed in previous works⁵⁹ and has been explained by suggesting that half of the polarons in a rr-P3HT/PC₇₀BM blend are formed on a sub 100 fs timescale and half on a timescale of tens of picoseconds.³¹ This is supported by more recent experimental and theoretical work on the prompt photocarrier production in such cells.⁶⁰ In any case the main difference between the ZnO-NPs and ZnO-NPs/DNA containing cells is in the long timescale of the polaron signal where more polarons are observed in the ZnO-NPs/DNA containing cells than in the ZnO only cells. This is taken as evidence that the more efficiently quenched excited excitons in the ZnO-NPs/DNA cells are more efficiently converted into free charges.

3. Conclusions

We have measured the femtosecond transient absorption spectra in the UV-Vis and NIR ranges of a series of complete working polymer:fullerene blend solar cells as a function of the composition of the electron transport layer of the cells. Spectral variations of the transient response in the visible range indicate a change in the long range intrachain order of the P3HT polymer when a layer of DNA coated ZnO nanoparticles is used as the electron transport layer. This suggests that the DNA can ‘imprint’ a different long range order of

the polymer when the blend is spin coated on top of the DNA containing ETL. Examination of the temporal traces corresponding to the excited exciton state populations show additional intermediate timescale decays (5 and 100 ps) and lower long-time trapping of the ZnO-NPs/DNA containing cells for the excited state. This has been interpreted as being due to more efficient dissociation of the initially formed exciton. Confirmation is obtained from a higher yield of the long lived P3HT cation polaron as observed in the NIR TA spectra. These observations of higher exciton dissociation into polarons in the ZnO-NPs/DNA containing cells is consistent with their measured PCEs. In view of these results we propose an interesting approach to improve the BHJ solar cells performance which consists of the insertion of a nano-layer between the ETL and the active blend, in this case a DNA nano-layer. This layer not only determines a change in the electronic properties of the contact but also, importantly, exerts control on the P3HT morphology (but possibly also on other polymers). Indeed, starting from these results different kinds of templating layers can be envisaged and tailored to optimize the P3HT morphology (or in general the electron donor polymer) and thus to improve the PCE.

4. Experimental Section

Materials

DNA (Deoxyribonucleic acid sodium salt from salmon testes, molecular mass of 1.3×10^6 Da ($\sim 2,000$ base pair) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Zinc oxide, dispersion nanoparticles (ZnO-NPs) of the average particle size less than 40 nm and with 20 wt.% concentration in water was also purchased from Sigma Aldrich. P3HT, Poly(3-hexylthiophene) (20 mg/ml in ortho-dichlorobenzene) and PC₇₀BM, [6,6]-Phenyl-C71-butyric acid methyl ester, (99.99%) were purchased from Solarmer and Solenne BV, respectively. Molybdenum oxide (MoO₃, 99.98% powder), ortho-dichlorobenzene and silver (Ag, wire Z 99.99%) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich.

Solar Cell Preparation

In the process of inverted solar cell device fabrication the ITO glass-covered substrates (Kintec, $-8 \Omega/\text{cm}^2$), are patterned with wet-etching in hydrobromic acid (HBr) and cleaned in ultrasonic bath in acetone and isopropanol for 10 min with each solvent. For the fabrication of ITO/ZnO-NPs/DNA/P3HT:PC₇₀BM/MoO₃/Ag solar cells ZnO-NPs solution for the thin film deposition was prepared by diluting 200 μl ZnO-NPs dispersion in 20 ml ethanol which was further stirred overnight at room temperature. ZnO-NPs thin film was deposited on ITO coated glass substrate by spin-coating at spin speed of 2500 rpm which was carried out and then annealed at 140°C for 20 minutes. The DNA solution was prepared first by dissolving 5 mg DNA fibers in 0.5 ml of deionized water until the solution becomes transparent and then 4.5 ml of methanol was added to dilute it to be 1 mg/ml concentration.⁴³ After overnight stirring at room temperature, the DNA solution was filtered using a 0.2 μm PVDF filter (NB: it is important to use this type of filter to obtain the films discussed in this article; the use of PTFE or polypropylene filters with the same pore size instead, resulted in DNA films with different optical and thickness properties) and then spin-coated on ITO coated glass substrate at spin speed of 3000 rpm over the ZnO-NPs thin film. The prepared ITO/ZnO-NPs/DNA samples were left in vacuum overnight for drying. The active layer P3HT:PC₇₀BM (1:0.7) was dissolved in ortho-dichlorobenzene and stirred at 75°C temperature overnight. Next, the blend solution was filtered using 0.22 μm pore sized PTFE filter and spin coated at 500 rpm which was followed by annealing at 130°C temperature for 10 minutes. At the end all substrates were transferred in the metal evaporator where MoO₃ (hole extracting interlayer) and silver top contact were thermally evaporated through a shadow mask at pressures below 10^{-6} mbar for a final thickness of 5 nm and 100 nm respectively. Each substrate contained 4 devices of 0.1 cm^2 area.

Transient absorption measurements and data analysis

The transient absorption measurements were performed by exciting the solar cells with the second harmonic of a 35 fs 810 nm Ti:Sapph laser with an intensity of $180 \mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$. The experiments were performed in a pseudo-reflectivity mode in which the focussed pump beam (spot size diameter $500 \mu\text{m}$) passes through the cell from the glass side, reflects from the Ag electrode and exits again through the glass with an incidence angle of 4° (see Figure 1 (a) for a schematic view of the pump-probe geometry). The probe beam for the UV-Vis TA experiments is generated by focussing $\sim 3 \mu\text{J}$ of 800 nm light into a CaF_2 crystal thus generating a white light continuum in the range 350 - 800 nm (the results here only show the range 450 - 750 nm), while the NIR continuum (800 - 1600 nm) is generated in a similar manner in a YAG crystal.

The fitting procedure to extract the time constants of the temporal behaviour of the PB_1 , PB_2 , PIA_3 , PIA_4 and PIA_5 signals is described fully in the supporting information. Furthermore, all time constants and weighting parameters are reported in Tables S1-S5.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the authors.

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Graphical TOC Entry

